

Automating a Quantitative Representation of Urban Form: Integrating Built Environment Analyses as Input for Studies Relating Tangible and Intangible Dimensions of Places

– Workshop Report –

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To study the effects of urban environments on intangible dimensions of places, such as place attachment, in terms of their urban planning principles requires for spatial configurations and patterns in the urban form to be identified in a systematic and reliable way, ensuring comparability and allowing the evaluation of different approaches to urban design. Built environments are traditionally broken down into constituent structures, often analysed in parallel, if not independently, to understand urban scenarios. As a result, the interrelationships between the structures as coexisting aspects are lost and, with it, part of the complex character of the urban scenarios. A methodological approach to automate urban analyses of tangible aspects and integrate the results into a quantitative representation of physical and design patterns of places was presented in a workshop held during the Fourth International Symposium on Spatial Information Science (PLATIAL'23) with the aim of gathering expert opinions and evaluate the methodology. Through the contributions and discussions, the strong need to consolidate a model to describe urban scenarios through the simultaneous consideration of multiple tangible aspects was identified. Likewise, the potential of the approach for exploring the interdisciplinary character of places and possible benefits of integrating different analysis and data gathering techniques was regarded during the workshop as positive.

Keywords: workshop; methodology; automatization; urban analysis; spatial configurations; place

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1 Introduction

Within the interdisciplinary field of environmental psychology, the concept of place attachment has been defined as pertaining to the emotional bonds between inhabitants and the contexts in which they carry out their lives, usually referring to a positive association with said places and thus indicative of place quality or of environments exhibiting quality of living conditions (Moulay et al., 2018). Such relations between people and places had been initially considered in the literature to derive from emotional/symbolic and functional bonds, corresponding to the concepts of place identity and place dependence, as sub-dimensions of place attachment (Stedman, 2003; Williams et al., 1992). This model has been subsequently complemented with further dimensions as, e.g., social bonding as representative of the social dimension of places (Luo et al., 2016) or regarded as influenced by familiarity, or cultural backgrounds and contexts (Low and Altman, 1992; Ujang and Zakariya, 2015).

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Parallel to this psychological dimension by which places can be regarded phenomenologically from the perception and cognition of their inhabitants and users, permanent processes of creation and transformation of places signify constant changes to these environments. Among the numerous ways in which cities continuously transform themselves, urban development projects (i.e., urban design projects) can be one of the most clear-cut modes in which urban environments are established or redefined, be them in the form of new urban areas or urban redevelopment projects, changing the contexts in which human life occurs under clear guidelines deriving from the design process. Such undertakings are directly creating or transforming places every time the resulting form of the urban context becomes 'alive' through the use given by its residents and users, for every environment becomes a 'place' when its spatiality and components, be them built or natural, are understood in terms of the relations, interactions, meanings, and experiences that humans have with them (Jenkins, 2004; Relph, 1976). Simultaneously, the character and qualities of the places originating from the physical environments produced by these processes of transformation are related to the guidelines and principles shaping their design. The success or failure of these new or transformed urban contexts as places can be thus said to be, even when not entirely, a result of the urban design principles implemented, of the focus or consideration given by its conception to different aspects of the urban reality, and also a consequence of its omissions or the neglect of given dimensions of urban life. The critique raised, e.g., in the German public discussion of the last decade against processes of city production, development, and intervention of urban areas, especially those produced by the real estate sector as a mean for economical production, refers not only to the physical characteristics or spatial configuration of said developments but also to their inability to provide liveable environments and to respond to current and future-oriented guidelines to urban life, to an evolving concept of urbanity, and to the central role of cities in shaping contemporary societies (Bundesinstitut für Bau-, Stadt- und Raumforschung, 2022; Deutsche Akademie für Städtebau und Landesplanung, 2014).

In this sense, an evaluation of the quality of the urban places that have resulted from different urban design approaches requires the analysis of non-tangible dimensions, as allowed, e.g., by the concept of place attachment, against the backdrop of the urban design patterns that can be read from the already resulting physical environment produced by the conception. Such an approach aiming to establish what features of the urban context promote positive feelings of bonding between people and places warrants the analysis of these two dimensions on already established and functioning neighbourhoods, in which such relations have already come to fruition. Here, the perspective of a 'reverse urbanism' approach, as suggested by Noyman et al. (2019), by which human behavioural patterns are used to evidence 'the success rates of highly performative urban places' and provide strong foundation for urban design, planning, and decision-making practices, is appeal to. But the need for 'sufficient input for "soft" psychological model parts and factors' (Vogelbacher et al., 2019) becomes essential. For this purpose, a systematic translation of urban design (i.e., spatial) configurations into quantitative data accounting multiple factors could serve as overarching yet deep representation of that tangible dimension and allow an understanding of the urban form without omitting its complexity. This quantitative description can then be analysed against intangible aspects of place in following steps of analysis. The automatization of these urban form analyses and the linking of their results to certain spatial components of the environment could simplify their integration into a coherent and multifaceted blueprint of urban areas, ensure comparability between case studies, and facilitate further research on the field.

A methodological approach aiming to automate different quantitative analyses of urban environments in terms of spatial configurations and urban design features, which would allow for the integration and simultaneous consideration of different dimensions of urban areas, has been put forward as discussion topic for a workshop carried out in the context of the Fourth International Symposium on Platial Information Science (PLATIAL'23) with the objective of gathering expert opinions on the methodology presented as well as valuable insights regarding further subjects, dimensions, and methods of analysis that could be included to this approach. The method itself, as well as the results of the workshop, are presented in the following pages of this report.

2 Methodological Approach

The complexity of urban environments arising from the multitude of interacting systems and factors, as well as from their constantly evolving nature, has traditionally been approached by means of its dissection in composing systems or layers, each of them representing different aspects of urban life and

the infrastructures that support them. Still, the cognition of urban surroundings by its inhabitants and users does not usually involve such differentiation. Urban reality is usually perceived as a mixture of all these interacting systems, wherein similarities and differences between places and their patterns can be recognized, while the particularities that makes these out can remain hard to pin-point. Familiar and contrasting situations are more easily identifiable for someone comparing places from the point of view of their own experience. In this sense, the inspection and focus on certain dimensions and aspects of places becomes highly relevant for the analysis of urban environments. With it, the depth and detail with which the world is observed can be intensified, but at the same time the comprehension of a given built environment in its integrating nature is bound to be left out. The contribution that current advances on computational techniques and capacity provide to the simultaneous examination of different aspects of urban form allows for this complexity to be approached systematically with increasingly more accessible resources. Bringing into view many systems at the same time while retaining their intricacy can be a daunting task, especially using traditional approaches. 'It may seem that these nondiscursive properties are elusive, or impossible to quantify, but the patterns are no less real for their complexity, and also there to be found by the machine' (Hanna, 2022). The field of urban analytics has made use of new forms of data as well as innovative computational approaches throughout the last decades to allow a closer look into these urban processes (Malleon et al., 2022).

Current technologies that have been intensely leveraged in this field have allowed for more aspects of urban reality to be brought into focus with increasing scopes of application and depth. They have allowed for previously existing methods of urban analysis to be carried out in greater extends, e.g., increasing the scales of analysis, the comprehensiveness of their application, and extend of variables considered. They have also allowed for other sources of information to be tapped and utilized more effectively as they could have before. At the same time, they have allowed for new methods of analysis to be developed, expanding the ways urban reality can be probed. Yet, the isolation of certain aspects of urban environments to evaluate their possible relations with aspects of urban life and the behaviour of people remains as the usual approach to exploring the interrelationships between tangible and intangible dimensions of places. With them, particular linkages between aspects of environment and behaviour can be thoroughly investigated, but the effect to which other unobserved factors can influence these interactions is left out of the scope of analysis.

The methodology being considered here seeks to approach the analysis of built environments as the sum of several of these different aspects. The automatization of (traditional or innovative) urban analyses and their integration into an inclusive image of urban neighbourhoods in terms of their tangible structures would allow for spatial configurations to be identifiable in terms of quantitative data. The aim is to reduce the complexity of urban environments for the purpose of exploring and understanding them, without overlooking the multiplicity of factors involved or exploring particular relationships in isolation. This integrative picture of built urban contexts that retains the inherit interrelations within their structures can be seen as a translation of the urban design principles applied to their conception and development, as these have materialized in the resulting urban environment, i. e., in the urban reality. To this effect, the approach integrates different quantitative analysis methods and transposes their results to the cartographic representation of the urban area to retain the spatial relations between them. Data on each analysis performed is stored in relation to different spatial components of the urban structure (buildings, plots, streets, and blocks) to serve as a multi-level, multi-dimensional depiction of the spatial configurations, which can be accessed throughout different scales of inspection depending on the requirements of further analyses relating intangible aspects of places. In this sense, this methodological approach is to be regarded as a part of a broader study relating the perception of urban places to their built form, through which the latter can be explored and described. Nevertheless, the application of this integrative method can be expanded to other purposes, as a mean to examine built environments in their complexity, for which the automatization of the process and accessibility to tools and sources of information becomes relevant.

Dimensions of Analysis. Starting from traditional methods of urban analysis, the following aspects of urban environments are considered within the scope of this methodology. An analysis of the built structure follows on the basis of aspects such as density, building typologies, and spatial arrangements such as street configurations, edges, barriers, and sightlines. In terms of uses and functions, the identification of land uses as pertaining to formal determinations, as well as the particular activities carried out in buildings, is complemented with the functions of open spaces and the structures they form, such as networks of public spaces and green spaces. The mobility dimension is overlaid to the

analysis of open spaces, considering not only the analysis of street networks in terms of their hierarchy and types, but also in terms of distribution, accessibility, and centrality-integration (space index). The analysis of modes of transportation complements this network analysis and allows for further aspects particular to each system (pedestrian, cycling, motorized, and public transport) to be also integrated (walkability, quality of infrastructures, restrictions, parking, frequencies, etc.).

Beyond these traditional layers of analysis of urban structures, the integration of innovative methods of analysis and data collection, which could provide further insights into the built environment, is seen as a possible way to expand the scope of the approach. To that effect, some methods have already been tentatively identified, such as multivariate density analysis, e.g., spacematrix (Berhauser Pont and Haupt, 2021); visibility analyses like 2D/3D isovist fields analysis (Wu et al., 2023); volume index/openness analysis (Zhao et al., 2020); and the use of geo-referenced data scraping. Techniques for mapping pedestrian behaviour using public GPS tracks or agent-based modelling (Malleon et al., 2022), as well as the analysis of traffic information, could complement mobility infrastructure analyses. Furthermore, remote sensing and image recognition techniques could provide a closer look at surface distribution patterns in streetscapes (Hamim et al., 2023) or the distribution of vegetation, and it could facilitate the surveying of design aspects in façades. However, the inclusion of these methods in the approach needs to be further evaluated and was also subject of discussion in the corresponding workshop.

Tools and Data Sources. Aiming towards the replicability of the approach, the selection of tools and data sources focusses on the use of accessible tools and information that, to the extent possible, are publicly available or can be freely used. For this purpose, QGIS, as an open-source geographic information system, is used as the main platform for integrating information from different sources, performing and automating spatial analyses, and spatially referencing the results of the different analyses. Within it, the model designer interface (Processing Modeler) is used as an entry-level mean for the automatization of the analyses, allowing the programming of complex processes through a graphical interface and facilitating the implementation of the methodology by users not qualified in programming languages. Geocoding functions integrated to QGIS that make use of readily accessible geodata (Nominatim) are used within the approach to translate semantic information like addresses and names of place to geo-referenced locations. The functionality of the software can also be further expanded by the use of open-source extensions, through which the integration of certain urban analysis can be achieved. Extensions like OSM Downloader or QNEAT3 (QGIS Network Analysis Toolbox) have been integrated so far.

Regarding data sources, the accessibility to information is ensured by the use of publicly-available data. In the German context, where the case studies of this study take place, basic cartographic information and geodata on a variety of topics can be accessed publicly and, depending on the state, without cost. This provides a reliable source of information that ensures to some extent the replicability and comparability of the studies, given that the standards for the geodata infrastructure (layers, fields, data-types, and metadata) are coordinated at the federal level through the GDI-DE (Geodateninfrastruktur Deutschland) and the implementation of the INSPIRE guidelines for the creation of infrastructure for spatial information in the European Union. The available information includes vector data (e.g., cadastre information, formal development plans, and UTM-tiles) and raster data (e.g., digital elevation model, digital orthophotos, and satellite image data), or 3D information (3D building models LoD2). Furthermore, open-source geodata from OpenStreetMap is also used as an important source to complement the cartographic information and geodata available through the official channels. Both sources can be subject of inconsistencies and missing information. For this reason, they are used simultaneously under the consideration of principles of availability and compatibility that arise from the automatization of the analyses, but that are applied retroactively and systematically throughout the process.

Projected Outcomes. The results of the different analyses are to be compiled at the building, plot, street, and block level as to be able to relate them to one another spatially. This information is stored within the different objects (areas and buildings) in the form of scores (continuous data) or types (categorical data) depending on the corresponding evaluation criteria for each analysis. Considered together, these different results are intended to provide a quantitative description of the spatial configurations of a given urban context that can be dynamically computed in relation to a particular place (e.g., residence) or sequences of places (e.g., path to work) for different respondents.

This allows for the information on the built environment to be matched not only generally to the place as a whole but to be regarded from the perspective of the inhabitants as individuals relating to their environment. When considered in relation to the broader urban area (e.g., at the neighbourhood level), the computation of the spatial configurations, participating structures, and the results of their evaluations can provide an overview that will allow the comparison of different study areas in terms of the statistical analysis of the measurements for each aspect integrated to the methodology. Further, on the basis of qualitative methods applied according to the aims of the overarching study (e.g., relating place attachment to built environment), the performance of the different case studies will also be comparable against the backdrop of their spatial configurations, i.e., of their urban design guidelines.

3 The Workshop

Within the framework of PLATIAL'23, one of the workshops carried out, titled 'Automatization of Spatial Analyses of Urban Areas', served the purpose of evaluating the methodological approach presented above and to gather expert opinions on the implementation and methods of analysis considered. The main question posed to the participants to introduce the topic and prompt the subsequent discussion read: 'How to automate spatial analyses to streamline a quantitative representation of the urban form, such that it can be used as input for further research into urban form and intangible aspects of place?'. The main objectives, as stated during the workshop, were to discuss the possibilities and challenges for the automatization of traditional and innovative urban analysis processes, to explore the scope of application of the generated data as features of geospatial components, and to discuss the potential and limits of using this approach as groundwork for further urban studies.

First, the topic was introduced to the participants, including the presentation of the current state of the development of the workflow in QGIS and its application in a particular case study, located around the neighbourhood of Phoenix See in Dortmund. The active participation of the attendees was structured in two phases. In the first part, named 'Exploring the Approach', the group was divided into two smaller subgroups with no more than ten participants to facilitate the discussion. The aim of this first phase was to prime the participants into pondering about the application of this method from their own research perspectives and to propose analysis methods and application scenarios for this methodology. For this, the discussion within the groups was divided into two sub-phases, correspondingly named 'Further Analyses' and 'Possible Applications'. Before starting, participants were given a handout containing questions to help guide the discussion in each sub-phase and where they should also document their contributions and thoughts in each subject. The discussion in each sub-phase followed the following structure: In the first 20 minutes, using the Think-Pair-Share moderation technique, participants were asked to first reflect by themselves on the questions at hand and then to discuss their thoughts with a neighbouring attendee, to finally share their contributions to the group. In the last 10 minutes foreseen for each sub-phase, with the help of a voluntary co-moderator, the group was asked to write down keywords summarizing their contributions on cards and to organize them in a whiteboard. In the case of the first sub-phase, contributions were to be evaluated through a low-hanging fruit analysis and placed accordingly on the whiteboard, following the corresponding diagram. Contributions to the second sub-phase were to be grouped by topics according to categories defined on the go by the participants. For the first sub-phase, under the title 'Further Analyses', the guiding question provided posed was 'What other types of analysis can be integrated to this approach?'. The work sheet invited the participants to share ideas regarding further features of urban environments to be considered for the analysis, (innovative) methods of urban/spatial analysis to be implemented, and sources of information/tools required. For the second sub-phase, titled 'Possible Applications', the main question on the work sheet read: 'How can these new layers of information be used as input data for further interdisciplinary research on places?'. Participants were inquired on aspects of place that could be explored with the approach, relevant data or relationships between parameters, and advantages and disadvantages that may come with applying the approach on the research topics suggested.

The whole group was brought back together for the second phase of the workshop after a short break. In this second part, the results of the first phase were presented by the co-moderators and a general evaluation was carried out with the objective of gathering the opinions of the participants regarding the overall conception, structure, and applicability of the methodological approach in its entirety. The evaluation was conducted through a series of general questions on the advantages,

disadvantages, suggestions, and concerns that the participants had identified when working on the topics of the first phase. This section was moderated using Mentimeter, an online platform with which the participants could respond to the questions through their mobile devices and afterwards see all answers offered by the group through the projector in the room and allowing the evaluation to take place at a steady pace and within the time available. After collecting the answers for each question, a short time was also allotted to ‘up-vote’ answers from other participants, which allowed a certain consensus on the commentaries to be expressed by the group, helping the author to identify focus points within the answers. At the end of the workshop, the participants were asked to share their concluding comments and thoughts on the topic. This gave them the opportunity to speak openly and express their opinions outside the framework provided by the assessment questions.

3.1 Responses and Contributions

During the first phase of the workshop, 12 participants documented their contributions in the provided work sheets. Through these, several suggestions were provided concerning the methods of analysis that could be integrated into the methodology, as well as possible application scenarios of this approach for further research, corresponding to the topics of the first and second sub-phases. The results of these sessions are summarized in the following paragraphs.

First Sub-Phase: Further Analysis. On the topic of further analyses that could be incorporated into the methodology valuable contributions were provided by the participants on all the guiding questions. The features of the urban environment suggested for consideration can be grouped under the following categories: environmental factors, such as micro-climate, weather, air quality, sound/noise levels, light pollution, daylight/shadows, wind, and smells; street furniture, like lighting elements, benches, planters/vegetation, electricity boxes, trash cans, and drinking fountains; mobility-related features, mainly those on or relating to sidewalks, like bike/scooter/car parking spaces, and bike lanes; features of the built environment, such as specific elements, like city gardening areas, ground surfaces, and façade elements (sequence of openings and façade rhythm); but also properties of the environment, such as building quality, mixture of uses, design glitches, urban thresholds and the porosity and transparency of structures; evolving aspects of place, like the history of the place, its development through time, architectural styles present, and maintenance status of buildings or areas; and lastly, experiential aspects of place, such as the feelings experienced by users (e.g., feeling of safety), local and global perceptions, and digital geographies (e.g., Curbspace).

The following methods of data collection and analysis were suggested by the participants to approach the aforementioned features of places: crowdsourcing for experiential aspects of place; remote sensing techniques, i.e., object detection, for streetscape elements and other built environment features; social sensing for social environments and local/global perceptions; simulations techniques, e.g., ENVI-met, for environmental aspects like micro-climate, wind speed, or solar radiation; VR experiences for digitally testing/exploring experiential aspects of place; machine learning techniques, e.g., GeoAI, for predictive analyses of local/global perceptions (casual reasoning) or for processing information from development plans; space index techniques, e.g. centrality/betweenness, for analysing mobility networks; as well as sentiment analysis, for processing information gathered in participation process. Finally, a series of analysis methods that were highly discussed in both groups and that could be referred to as ‘sensescapes’, aimed at approaching different types of sensory information that could be also mapped and included in the methodology. The analysis of these ‘smooth’ scapes included, e.g., the mapping of soundscapes, smellscapes, tastescapes, and stressscapes. These could be regarded independently or in terms of co-occurrences, i.e., of overlapping situations regarding more than one of these dimensions, possibly pointing towards (positive or negative) points of interest in urban places.

Possible sources of information suggested by the participants included: sensor data (recording devices, drones, lidar, thermometers, air quality; IoT sensors); imagery (photography, satellite images, 360° photos, e.g., Google Street View); CCTV footage (safety); surveys/interviews; natural language descriptions; mapathons (participatory mapping sessions); XPlan-GML data (XPlanung data format for legally binding development plans in the German context); thematic maps (e.g., municipal noise maps, lighting concepts, monument register, depth maps); as well as publicly-available cadastral and cartographic data. At the end of the session, the participants evaluated the discussed approaches in terms of cost-benefit by placing cards with keywords regarding the methods of gathering and analysing data on a low-hanging-fruit diagram (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Low-Hanging-Tree Analysis. The contributions of the participants on the topic 'Further Analyses' of Phase 01a, based on the photographic documentation of the workshop whiteboards.

Second Sub-Phase: Possible Applications. The second half of the initial phase was affected by time constraints resulting from very active discussions during the first half. Nevertheless, some of the participants were able to document their thoughts on the possible research scenarios in which this methodology could be applied, the aspects of place that could be explored through it, relevant data, and parameters the possible relationship of which could be studied and the advantages and disadvantages of the application of this approach.

Some of the possible applications suggested included, e.g., studying physical well-being and the feeling of comfort when moving through places, for which possible relations between demographic data and cycling infrastructure could be studied within an urban area. Here, the need for accurate sensor data and possible issues with data protection were expressed as concerns, as well as possible misalignments between the subjective feelings and the objective situation. The exploration of possible relations between street furniture and mobility patterns was also proposed, whereby the location of these elements regarding surrounding building typologies could also be analysed. For this approach, the participant saw as advantages of the method the possibility to integrate innovative data sources and new analysis methods but considered that it could be difficult to implement and deemed it not cost-effective. Another participant suggested two possible research applications: to explore how unique the experiences of inhabitants are, and to study the impact of seasons on places. For these, the analysis of possible relations between parameters like a neighbourhood's calculated walkability and the actual experience of users (e.g., children) regarding distances to daily goals, or between green spaces and changes in temperature across the year, could be explored. Advantages identified for these research approaches are the capacity to model reality more closely and the possibility to test and measure the impact of changes on places, while the overflow of options and possibilities and the risk of overconfidence in the model were identified as disadvantages. The exploration of the concept of vitality in urban places was also suggested as a possible field of application, where a reported sense of vitality could be analysed against parameters like micro-climate (environmental comfort), safety, local community, and mixture of uses. For this approach, the participant identified as disadvantages of the method the possibility that it may not be accessible (user-friendly) for some researchers, that some events are unpredictable, and that the model may be based too much on physical aspects. The speed and replicability of the method in other contexts were regarded as advantages. Another suggestion was the exploration of spatial extent, accessibility, and the integration of places with other surrounding places, as research approaches where this method could be implemented. While considering that the approach offers to deliver much information on places, the participant expressed concerns regarding the complexity of data acquisition as well as questioning how well the method can capture what makes places.

3.2 Evaluation of the Approach

As mentioned before, once the teams had presented the results of the first session to the whole group, the second phase of the workshop focussed on evaluating the method presented as a whole, i. e., as a methodological approach for automating and merging quantitative data that can represent tangible dimensions of built environments and its use as input for exploring possible relationships with intangible aspects of places. In that sense, the feedback goes beyond the advantages and disadvantages previously reported, for it no longer referred to the application of the methodology to explore a specific topic. The contributions of the participants to the different questions posed have been summarized and are presented following the level of agreement shown by the whole group, as allowed by the up-voting function of the Mentimeter platform used.

The participants identified as positive aspects of the approach the possibility to visualize complex relationships between people and places, allowing to explore interdisciplinary aspects effectively through the automation of analyses and enriching the information available by aggregating it with other data. The possibility to identify ideas or relations that are not immediately evident and to test and measure the impact of changes were also pointed out as advantages. As shortcomings or disadvantages the attendees highlighted the need for time and effort by the process of data acquisition, while also pointing out the difficulty of creating datasets including subjective data that is hard to grasp, even more if the research topic requires it on a large scale. Additionally, some participants considered the method to be too focused on physical aspects of places, while others warned about the amount of data required and the obfuscation, possible biases, and omissions that can arise from taking too many aspects into consideration simultaneously. Possible issues with data availability and data protection were also indicated. When asked about recommendations for the approach, in terms of possibilities for improvement, the participants were somehow divided between the inclusion or non-inclusion of surveys into the methodology, thus voting equally on both suggestions. It was also suggested that the scope of the research should be narrowed down and the data sources selected more carefully. Moreover, the recommendation to remain enthusiastic about the approach was also highlighted by the group. Finally, the participants responded to potential challenges and concerns that they may foresee by the application of the method. Here, the group emphasized caution regarding correlations between parameters that may arise when researching their relationships. They also pointed out the scale of the project regarding available resources and expertise, warned about possible errors due to outdated datasets, and addressed how decision-making processes can remain independent of analysis results.

4 Conclusions

The workshop allowed a great opportunity to gather expert insights and opinions on the methodology being presented for the purpose of exploring relations between tangible and intangible aspects of urban places. Through their contributions and suggestions, the participants have shared similar concerns on issues that had previously been identified by the author during the conception of this methodological approach, mainly possible difficulties with the interpretation of relationships identified between aspects of these two dimensions, and technical, organisational, and even theoretical issues that may arise given the scope and integration of a considerable number of analysis and parameters. Nevertheless, the opportunities and benefits that this approach may provide have also been expressed by the participants of the workshop, amongst which its potential for exploring the interdisciplinary character of places, the aim to leverage traditional and innovative data gathering techniques and analysis methods, and the possibility to integrate existing and new datasets can be emphasized.

During the discussions and the joint exploration of the approach, it has become evident that the role of the different aspects of a place to be incorporated and analysed needs to be more clearly defined. Furthermore, the need to develop a strong framework through which these different parameters can be combined into, and interpreted as, meaningful spatial configurations has also been recognized. Through it, the traces of the urban design guidelines behind (contemporary) urban development projects can be discerned in the realized urban environment. This is particularly important not only for the validity of the methodology but above all for the intended goal of approaching the complexity of urban environments and evaluating their qualities and attributes against the background of the residents' perceptions of places.

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